

Introducing Overture: A Cloud-Native Global Map

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Summary

The Overture Maps Foundation is a new initiative which combines multiple sources of spatial data to produce a suite of new globally consistent and interoperable geospatial data. Addresscloud, a geospatial services company, is a member of the Overture Maps Foundation, contributing to the design, development and proto-applications of the data. It is anticipated that such data will be of interest to the GIS community in the UK and abroad. In this paper we introduce the Overture project, key themes and concepts of interoperability. We also explore the idea of cloud-native data and close by introducing some prototype global use cases and processing flowlines for consumption of the Overture data.

KEYWORDS: data, open source, topography, global reference system,

1. Introduction

The utility of open geospatial data-sets with global coverage for research and commercial applications is well established. Satellite platforms collecting geospatial data, which is subsequently available under open and permissive licenses, are widely used in a range of areas, including global climate monitoring, disaster response, and meteorology. However, the availability of topographic geospatial data that is globally consistent, and openly available, is more limited. The most well-known example is the crowd-sourced OpenStreetMap project (Hacklay, 2020), which has successfully been used in a range of diverse applications from sanitation network planning (Holderness et al., 2016) to disaster risk management (Meier, 2015). However, OpenStreetMap data has limited coverage in some geographies, and inconsistent attribution (Ballantyne and Berragan, 2023). The widespread use of mobile mapping applications, including Google Maps and Apple Maps indicates the existence of globally-consistent geospatial data, but these are often prohibitively commercial or unavailable for research purposes.

The advent of scalable cloud computing infrastructure has been critical in the development of global-scale Geographic Information Systems (Pilone et al., 2019, Holderness and Varley, 2020). Machine learning, combined with cloud computing infrastructure, now affords the development of new processes which can efficiently analyse, curate, and distribute global geospatial data at a scale which was previously not possible. Overture uses these technologies to ingest imagery from satellites and aerial platforms, and combine them with existing topographic data from open source such as OpenStreetMap, to create new globally-consistent data.

2. Overture Map Themes

Overture maps data is split into themes (see Table 1). All data is held in one entire schema that is split into parquet files of a similar size. The data is partitioned by each of the themes which allows users to extract data for that theme only.

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Table 1 Overture Maps Themes

Theme	Description	Features Count
Admins	Administrative Boundaries	4,299,412
Base	Contextual Basemap	148,614,325
Buildings	Human-made structures with roofs or interior spaces	2,342,397,546
Places	Point representations of facilities, services, or amenities	57,619,504
Transportation	Infrastructure of global travel for people and objects	640,869,734

3. Cloud-native Geospatial

One of the issues with previously accessing global topographic map data (such as OSM) was that the tools and technology weren't able to scale to process the required volume of data. An entire planet file of OSM data is 90 gigabytes and this needs to be fed through desktop tools using powerful hardware to extract features of interest the entire potentially process taking days. Ultimately this meant that routine processing of such data on a global scale is often not feasible..

More recently both Microsoft and Google have released open building datasets, both created using machine learning algorithms. This affords new data which is globally available, but is significantly voluminous. To meet the challenge of processing and accessing these data, the Overture team has opted to use cloud-native tools and data formats. Cloud-native formats enhance user efficiency by enabling streamlined interaction with vast data sets, saving time and resources. The approach reduces research costs and accelerates innovation by eliminating the need to download and store unnecessary data copies before project commencement (<https://cloudnativegeo.org/about/>) At Addresscloud we have used this approach to analyse big datasets in a way that was not possible only a few years ago. Tools such as DuckDB allow users to stream remote data in columnar formats such as Parquet , and subsequently query, modify and create new datasets based on subsets of the data in near real-time..

4. Global Entity Reference System

A key part of the Overture data schema is the Global Entity Reference System (GERS) This allows for the structuring, encoding, and referencing of map data to a shared universal reference. This will provide a mechanism to easily conflate datasets from different providers based on a specific GERS ID assigned to each feature (<https://docs.overturemaps.org/gers/>). The GERS is created by combining the h3 index that contains the center of the feature, a two digit identifier for the theme and a geohash of the feature itself. The use of the h3 index allows buildings to be cross referenced against h3 cells to speed up spatial querying where the h3 grid is available. We will explore this more in the oral presentation.

5. Processing Methodologies and Applications

We have been processing cloud-native parquet data from Overture in a variety of ways. This has included using DuckDB to analyse the data and stream areas of interest on a local machine. DuckDB is an in-process SQL OLAP database management system that is simple to use but extremely

powerful and fast when used with parquet data. Once we have the data we need for a particular project we use GDAL/OGR2OGR to load to our internal PostGIS database server or convert into FlatGeobuf files. These are subsequently used to create vector tiles for use in our front-end applications. For performing large-scale spatial operations and analytics we are able to import the raw parquet into BigQuery to take advantage of clustering and parallel processing it offers. Once processing has been completed it is exported for use in client-side applications.

We have started to use Overture data, in particular the buildings dataset, to form the basis for our data offerings in Europe and the United States. We have cut the buildings data against other datasets such as flooding extents to give a flood score to each building . We will describe this further in the oral presentation.

6. Summary

The Overture foundation has successfully applied cloud native geospatial technologies to the creation and delivery of new global scale topographic data products. In this paper we have examined the different themes of the new data and explored some of the potential cloud-native processing methodologies that can be used to analyse this data.

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<https://overturemaps.org/overture-2024-02-15-alpha-0-release-notes/>

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